

Various Income Generating activities and its implementation in Kanyaka Agro-farm (Jamugurighat, Sonitpur)

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Abstract

Income generation can help to overcome food insecurity, when economic factors are a fundamental cause of food insecurity. The food security programs aims to help the population survive today, but also to live better tomorrow, and in this sense the Income Generating Activities (IGA) serve as important alternatives of income generation. Income generation simply means gaining or increasing income or money that an individual or business receives in exchange for providing a good or service after investing capital. It can also be defined as small scale projects that create an income source to individual beneficiaries or beneficiary group whilst promoting; the principal right of self-determination and the objectives of integration, reputation and re – integration (FAO-2011).

The purpose of this study was to identified various Income-Generating Activities of Kanyaka agro-farm and its implementation. It specially looked at how the community of kanyaka established by creating job opportunities and what are the different types of income generating activities supported by kanyaka. The society “Bharaliparia Kanyaka Bohumukhi Paam” (Kanyaka) was incorporated in september 2016 with an objective of starting multi – cropping projects on the flood plains of Jia Bharali River. It is located at Sheelabandha Gaon Panchayat in Sonitpur District of Assam. The extension is 26°44'16"N to 26°46'30"N latitude and 92°52'30"E to 92°53'45"E longitude. The Kanyaka is developed with the objectives of integrated farming practices, but due to the low quality of soil, area has facing various problems in the agricultural sector as well as in the other sectors, due to which a large amount of impact has shown in terms of its inputs and outputs. The study area is facing environmental problems like flood, sand deposition, erosion in monsoon season. The paper mainly focused on identification of various income generating activities supported by Kanyaka agro-farm, to find the income generating activities in terms of its inputs and outputs and to find the market accessibility of kanyaka farm to its nearby area with special reference

to Tezpur town. The research paper is prepared with the help of primary and secondary sources of data. The questionnaire method, personal observation, interview and GPS location is used in this articles. The data are collected, analysis and interpreted with the helped of excel software, where different charts, bar and diagram are used in this paper.

During the study, it was observed that the poverty of the surrounding area is one of the noticeable problems of Kanyaka. But they have taken various steps towards poverty alleviation in the study area. The study tries to investigate how income-generating activities are supported by the kanyaka with the intention to contribute towards poverty alleviation and upliftment of community living standard of the region in general.

Keywords: *Kanyaka agro-farm, income generating, economic activities, poverty eradicate etc.*

1. Introduction:

Income generation can help to overcome food insecurity when economic factors are a fundamental cause of food insecurity and when food is available in local markets, but lack of money is the main difficulty faced by the vulnerable population. The food security programs aims to help the population survive today, but also to live better tomorrow, and in this sense the IGA serve as important alternatives. Income generation simply means gaining or increasing income or money that an individual or business receives in exchange for providing a good or service after investing capital. It can also be defined as small scale projects that create an income source to individual beneficiaries or beneficiary group whilst promoting; the principal right of self-determination and the objectives of integration, reputation and re-integration (FAO-2011).

The society “Bharaliparia Kanyaka Bohumukhi Paam” (Kanyaaka) was incorporated September 2016 with an objective of starting multi-cropping projects in 2000 acres of barren land on the flood plains of Jia Bharali River. It is located at Sheelabandha Gaon Panchayat in Sonitpur District of Assam. The coordinates are 26°44'16"N to 26°46'30"N latitude and 92°52'30"E to 92°53'45"E longitude. The kanyaka is developed with the objectives of integrated farming practices, but due to the low quality of soil, area has facing various problems in the agricultural sector as well as in the other sector. Due to which a large amount of impact has shown in terms of its inputs and outputs. The study area is facing other environmental problems like flood, sand deposition, erosion in rainy season. Rivers are our

valuable asset. They provide economic benefits to the people in various ways and made human civilization flourish since ancient civilization. It is an important source of livelihoods for the basin communities (Kgathi et al., 2006). In study area river Jia Bharali plays an important role in the establishment of kanyaka .

The purpose of this study was to identify various Income-Generating Activities of kanyaka agro-farm and its implementation. It specially looked at how the community of kanyaka established by creating job opportunities and what are the different types of income generating activity supported by kanyaka.

During the study, it has founded that the poverty of the surrounding area is one of the noticeable problems of kanyaka. But they have taken various steps to poverty alleviation in the study area. Most of those steps have however little no impact and have shown no signs of sustainability in the community. At the present time the non-governmental organisation has been increasing rapidly but their contributions to development remains limited. As a result, there are various evaluations for determining the success of income-generating projects as they fall under the category of NGOs.

In an attempt to eradicate poverty, the kanyaka Bohumukhi paam has funded many income-generating activities to improve their economic activities within communities. These income-generating activities were introduced as one of the poverty-alleviation strategies. Thus, income-generating activities are supported by the kanyaka with the intention to contribute towards poverty alleviation. However, despite such activities, poverty remains high in the surrounding region of kanyaka and it is not clear whether these activities are actually doing what they originally set out to do. Thus, identifying the income-generating activities supported by kanyaka by checking whether or not they are effective in the alleviation of poverty in the communities is a positive check or negative check. Hence, this study attempted to identify these income-generating activities and their inputs and output results.

2. Objectives:

1. Identification of various income generating activities supported by Kanyaka agro-farm.
2. To find the income generating activities in terms of its inputs and outputs.
3. To find the market accessibility of kanyaka farm to its nearby area with special reference to Tezpur town.

3. Databases & Methodology:

According to kothari (2004), research methodology is systematic way used by researcher to solve a research problem. The author further defines research methodology as the science of establishing how the research has done (kothari 2004). This research methodology is the philosophy or general principle which guides the research.

The database & methodology are the techniques that were used to collect data from the authorities and institution for this study. Questionnaires and the personal interviews were the techniques that used to collect data for the research purpose. The study was based on both primary and secondary sources.

Figure 1: Database & Methodology

Primary source of data:

As the present study was based on both primary and secondary data source. The Primary data were collected by interview on 26th of February and 17th of March, 2023 at “Bharaliparia Kanyaka Bohumukhi Paam” (kanyaka). The data were collected through questionnaires, personal interviews with the authorities and official members of the institute as well as hotel managers and the distributor of the goods.

3.1 Methodology:

The methodology used in this paper is based on questionnaires, after the collection of different types of information about the income generating activities such as agriculture; pisciculture, dairy farming etc. and then these information's were tabulated in different categories. After the tabulation of these information in different income generating activities, analysis were done using simple graph, pie charts using MS-Excel.

4. Study area:

The society “Bharalipara Kanyaka Bohumukhi Paam” (Kanyaka) was incorporated September 2016 with an objective of starting multi-cropping projects in 2000 acres of barren land on the flood plains of Jia Bharali River. It is located at Sheelabandha Gaon Panchayat in Sonitpur District of Assam. Kanyak Multipurpose Farm is located between 26°44'16"N to 26°46'30"N latitude and 92°52'30"E to 92°53'45"E longitude in the Eastern Himalayas. Kanyaka Multipurpose Farm is bordered by Dholaibil Kendra to the north, Jamugurihat and Goal villages to the south, Chaki Ghat and Gataimra to the south and Bharali River, one of the tributaries of the mighty The Brahmaputa River, to the west. The kanyaka bahumukhi paam was transformed over approx. 7.454 km² of arid land into lush field by starting a multi-cropping initiative.

Figure 2: Map of study area a) Location of Assam in India, b) Sonitpur district within Assam, c) Location map of Kanyaka agro-farm

5. Concept of income generating activities

Income generation can help to overcome food insecurity when economic factors are a fundamental cause of food insecurity and when food is available in local markets but lack of money is the main difficulty faced by the vulnerable population. The food security programs aim to help the population survive today, but also to live better tomorrow, and in this sense the income generating activities serve as important alternatives. Income generation simply means gaining or increasing income or money that an individual or business receives in exchange for providing a good or service after investing capital. It can also be defined as small scale projects that create an income source to individual beneficiary or beneficiaries group whilst promoting; the principal right of self-determination and the objectives of integration, reputation and re-integration (FAO-2011).

It should be noted that income-generating activities can take many forms. Originally, the term was used only by economists to explain the intricacies of a nation's economy. However, it is now quite widely used to cover a range of productive activities by people in any given community. Thus, in the current context, an income-generating activity simply means those

activities affecting the gaining or increasing of income by an individual person or community. (Kasikazi-2015).

According to Niekerk (2009), income generating activities are the activities focused on creating opportunities for communities to productively use locally available resources to develop less state dependent, more self-reliant households and communities able to care for themselves. Income generating activities focuses on using locally available resources to the benefit of the entire community.

As we know, from long time income generating activities provide us various additional benefits in different fields which improve the well-being of the communities as well as empowerment, reduce poverty, self-reliance and in the development of communities.

According to Revolving Loan Fund report (2002), income generating activities are, small-scale projects that create an income source to individual beneficiaries or beneficiary groups whilst promoting the principal right to self-determination and the objectives of integration, repatriation and re-integration. Danish Refugee Council (2002) uses the notion of income generation relatively broadly and as a cover term for a wide variety of activities such as micro-credit; grant-skills and vocational training; business training; cash or food for work (asset creation) schemes; local economic development initiatives; and even small and medium enterprise development.

In the strict sense of the term, income generation activities are aimed at creating a financial income. Income generating activities however, may also aim at positive effects in terms of empowerment, self-reliance and community development (Ison, 1996).

According to ACF International (2009), there are three ways income can be generated: Firstly, income-generating activities do not always mean immediate monetary gain, although, in the end, money is used to place a measurable value on the goods and services people produce. An example of an income-generating activity which does not lead to initial monetary gain would be a situation where a productive person produces enough food to feed him or herself as well as his or her family. In such a case, skills have been used to meet immediate needs and, thus, monetary savings have been achieved. Furthermore, a monetary value can be placed on the food produced and, in this way; the food can be viewed as an income (ACF International, 2009).

Secondly, a person can generate income by the astute investment of existing resources. An example of such income generation would be the development of a piece of land through planting a crop for sale. The money gained from selling the crop would be considered

income. Another example would be an indirect form of investment through bank savings or the purchase of part of ownership (i.e. shares) in a productive enterprise such as a business. Money generated from such investments is then deemed income (ACF International, 2009).

Thirdly, people can generate income by using their skills to serve others person, who then pay them for the use of those skills. That is, individuals can utilise their skills to earn wages. Such 'skills-for-wages' income can be generated in various ways, for example: through self-employment, working for others, or by adding to personal resources through investment (ACF International, 2009).

Finally, according to the United Nations Development Program Report (1997), the limits of a welfare-oriented response to the growing poverty crisis are well-recognized. Therefore, many development agencies and governments are increasing their emphasis on assisting people to secure income through their own efforts, rather than relying on state welfare and subsidies. Such approaches are often categorised as income-generating activities and cover initiatives as diverse as small business promotion; cooperative undertakings; job creation schemes; sewing circles; credit and savings groups; and youth training programmes. It is sometimes argued that, education and health provision; legal and political changes; and global economics also all affect the abilities of people to secure an income.

'Income-generating activities' refers to activities focussed on creating opportunities for communities to productively use locally-available resources in order to develop less state dependent and more self-reliant households and communities that are able to take care of themselves. Thus, income-generating activities focus on productively using locally-available resources as a means of benefitting the entire community (Richard, 2012:14).

5.1 Types of Income Generating Activities (I.G.A)

For most people around the world, generating income is a necessity, and it is done in order for them to survive. In study area they were started generating income activities for the commercial purpose. But unfortunately, these activities become major source of income for the neighbouring area which becomes most important for the local people to survive. In my study area, we have identified various source of income generating activities, among them 5 income generating activities is taken for the analysis purpose.

1. Agriculture
2. Dairy farming
3. Poultry farming
4. Swine husbandry
5. Pisciculture

Table 1: Showing average annual income from different sources

Types	Income in lakh	Percentage
Agriculture	38.5	13.53
Dairy farming	193.9	68.15
Poultry	9	3.16
Swine husbandry	2.8	0.98
Pisciculture	40	14.05
Total	284.5	100%

Source: Primary survey, 2023

Figure 3: Showing percentage wise distribution of income.

The above figure 3 showing the percentage wise distribution of incomes from different sector where 68.15 percent of income is from dairy farming, and followed by agriculture 13.53 percent, pisciculture 14.05 percent, poultry farming 3.16 percent, and swine 0.98 percent.

Table 2: Showing permanent employment of different sectors in person.

Types	Agriculture	Dairy	Poultry	Swine	Pisciculture	Total
Employment	100	24	4	4	5	137

Source: Primary survey, 2023

Figure 4: Permanent employment of different sector.

The above figure 4 showing the enrolment of permanent employment in different sector in person where 100 persons is from agriculture and followed by dairy 24 persons, poultry 4, swine 4 and pisciculture 5 persons.

Agriculture as a type of income generating activity

Agriculture is also considered to be the best vehicle to reduce rural poverty. This is because, in most developing countries, agriculture and agriculture-related activities provide most of the employment in rural areas. Agriculture contributes to poverty alleviation at rural, urban and national levels in the following ways:

- Provision of food;
- Employment creation;
- Increase of real wages; and
- Improvement of farm income

As we know, India is an agro-based country and most of the country's GDP has come from agriculture sector. In study area agriculture plays a vital role for creating job opportunities for the people of surrounding area through the whole year. The study focuses on some major cultivation of the area which plays an important role for agriculture sector such as Banana, rice and mustard cultivation.

Table 3: Details of major crop cultivation.

Types	Area (Bigha)	Production	Income in lakhs
Mustard	500	2000 mun	20
Rice	700	12 mun	3.5
Banana	40	-	15
Total	1240	-	38.5

Source: Primary survey, 2023

Table 4: Details showing income of major crops

Crops	Income in lakhs	Percentage
Mustard	20	52
Rice	3.5	9.09
Banana	15	38.94
Total	38.5	100

Figure 5: Showing income level of 3 major crops

Findings showed that agriculture is one of the main incomes generating activity of kanyaka. The researcher took 3 major crops cultivation of kanyaka for the study such as Mustard, Rice and Banana. The above figure 5, shows the seasonal income level where a large percentage of income generate from mustard cultivation about 52%, (20 Lakhs), and followed by Banana about 38.94% (15 lakhs), and Rice about 9.09% (3.5 lakhs).

Dairy farming

Dairy farming is the branch of agriculture that encompasses the breeding, rising, and utilization of dairy animals, primarily cows for the product of milk and the various dairy products processed from it.

In study area researcher found two types of dairy farm, such as cow farm and buffalo farm as buffalo's milk is also produced in commercial quantities in India. In cow farm we have identified three breeds of dairy cows such as australian, local and Gir for the purpose of dairy products. As pasture is the natural feed for the dairy animals and abundance of good pasture provides most of the requirements of a good dairy farming. kanyaka provide a vast area of grassland where cows and buffaloes are on pasture through all the year. Besides the pasture kanyaka also provide some nutrient food to keep the balance of milk production. A disease is one of the greatest problems of the dairy farm. Kanyaka management system look after the cleanliness, sanitization, isolation of sick, to keeping premises free of hazards that might cause of injury and infection.

Figure 6: flow chart showing the dairy farm of kanyaka

Cow farm:

Table 5: Details of cow farm

Species of cow	No. of cow	Annual Milk Production (in litre)	Annual Income	Total income
Local	300	81000	4050000	16,200,000
Australian	280	145800	7290000	
Giri	220	97200	4860000	
Total	800	324000		

Table 6: Annual Milk Production

Variety of cow	Annual Milk Production (In liter)	Percentage
Local	81000	25
Australian	145800	45
Gir	97200	30
Total	324000	100%

Source: Primary survey, 2023

Figure 7 : Annual Milk Production

Findings showed that in the cow farm there were total 800 of cows where three main types of cow breeds were seen such as local, Australian, and Gir. The above figure 7 showed Annual milk production, where a large percentage of milk were produced by Australian cow breeds about (45%), second highest milk were produced by Gir about (30%), and about (25%) were produced by local cows. From that it is shown the cow farm plays an important role to creating income generation activity where they gave employment to the 18 persons. They earned total annual income Rs. 16,200,000 from 324000 litre annual milk production.

Plates 1: Showing Cow shelter

Buffalo farm

Table 7: Detail Showing Data set of Buffalo farm.

Income generating activity	No. of Buffalo	No. of workers	Annual Milk Production (In Lt.)	Annual Income	Total Income
Buffalo	32	6	36,500	21,90,000	21,90,000

Source: Primary survey, 2023

Figure 8: showing annual milk production (in liter) and annual income

From analyzing the above table 7, and the figure 8 the finding showed that in buffalo farm they produced 36500 liters of milk from the 32 buffalos and their annual income from the farm is Rs.21, 90,000. It's also found that 6 working people are engaged in the farm.

Plates 2: Showing buffalo farm of kanyaka

Poultry farming

Poultry farming is the raising of birds domestically or commercially, primarily for meat and eggs. Chicken is one of the greatest animals for poultry farming. It's been 10th month of started poultry farming in study area, and the chicken breeds are taken from kolkata for the purpose of commercial eggs production. The kanyaka invest in poultry farm about five lakhs and produced best egg quality in north east. About 3700 eggs were produced by kanyaka daily. For the protection of chicken breeds the management used cleanliness and sanitization of the farm. The feeding, watering, egg gathering and cleaning operation are highly mechanized in kanyaka's poultry farm.

Table 8: Showing data set of Poultry farm

Type	No. of chicken	No. of workers	Monthly Egg Production	Monthly Income
Chicken	4000	03	104160	90000

Source: Primary survey, 2023

Figure 9: Showing monthly income and egg production

Findings showed that in chicken farm that there were 4000 of chickens. The above figure 9 shows monthly egg production and monthly income from the farm. Where they produced total 104160 eggs monthly and monthly income is Rs. 90000. From this it can be said that poultry farming plays an important role in generating income sources.

Plates 3: Showing poultry farming

Swine Husbandry

Swine husbandry or pig farming is the raising and breeding of domestic pig for the purpose of commercial meat production. Pigs or domestic swine have been raised for their meat since ancient time. In study area researcher have found three pigs farm where three varieties of pig breeds were seen. Corn is usually the basic feed for the pigs, although the wheat and other foods are often included in their diet. The pigs were supplies to the nearest daily market, Chariduar, and Sootea market for the purpose of meat.

Table 9: Detail showing data set of Pig farm.

Type	No. of pigs	No. of worker	Production (In 3 month)	Income (In 3 month)
Pig farm	65	5	40	70000

Source: Primary survey, 2023

Table 10: Detail showing production of pigs in 3 months.

Variety of pigs	Production	Percentage
Yorkshire	17	42
Hampshire	09	23
Null	14	35
Total	40	100

Source: Primary survey, 2023

Figure 10: Pig Production

Finding showed that in swine husbandry there were total 65 of pigs where 3 main types of pig breeds were seen such as Yorkshire, Hampshire and Null. The above figure 10 shows the pig production in 3 months where a large percentage of pigs were produced by Yorkshire about (42%) and the second highest were produced by Null pig breeds (35%) and about (23%) were produced by Hampshire pig breeds. From that it is shown that the pig farm plays an important role to creating income generation activity where they gave employment to the 5 persons. They earned total annual income Rs. 70000 in 3 months.

Pates 4: Showing pig farm

Pisciculture

Pisciculture is a process of growing fish and selling it or using its products for domestic or commercial use. Pisciculture provide us fish food, cod liver oil etc. In kanyaka researcher have found a huge area is covered by pisciculture about 11000 bigha's. Where they breeds different types of seeds of fishes. They have artificial ponds for pisciculture and aerator use for oxygen supply to the ponds.

Table 10: Details showing data set of fisheries

Type of iga	No. of total ponds	No. of artificial ponds	Capacity (2022-23)	Production (2022-23)	Area
Fishery	12	02	10 CR.	15 CR.	11000 Bigha

Source: Primary survey, 2023

Figure 11: Showing no. of total ponds and artificial ponds.

Figure 12: Showing fishing capacity and production.

Findings showed that the Pisciculture of kanyaka which covers an area about 11000 bigha. The above figure 11 shows the total no of ponds (12) and the no. of artificial ponds (2). And the figure 12, showed the fishing capacity about 10 crore.

Plates 5: Ponds within kanyaka

6. ROLE OF INCOME GENERATING ACTIVITIES OF KANYAKA IN TEZPUR MARKET:

Figure 13: Flow chart showing market pattern of kanyaka in Tezpur.

The society “**Bharaliparia** Kanyaka Bohumukhi Paam” (Kanyaka) is covering a large market of surrounding area like Jamugurihat, Tezpur, Dhekiajuli, Sootea, Dhalibil, Balipara, Chariduar, Tupia, Khanamukh and so on by distributing their goods from various sectors like agriculture, pisciculture, goods from dairy farming, and poultry farming.

The above figure 13 shows the market pattern of kanyaka in Tezpur, as the Tezpur brings most of the goods directly from kanyaka to the center point named as Prayassh. The kanyaka has other centers in Tezpur known as daily needs departmental store, and Bhogali. Prayassh has two sub-branches in chandmari and parbatinagar. The above figure 13 shows that prayassh distribute goods in two form through retailers (direct sale to customers), and through volunteers (indirectly sale to the customers through home delivery).

Figure 14: Market accessibility of Kanyaka agro-farm to its nearby area with special reference to Tezpur

GOODS FROM KANYAKA IN TEZPUR

Figure 15: flow chart showing goods from kanyaka in Tezpur

The above **figure 15** shows the goods bring from kanyaka to Tezpur market. Where various goods are supplying through the Prayassh which is the major center of kanyaka. Its brings major products of kanyaka such as- dairy product (milk, sweets, paneer, curd, honey), snacks (mithi, namkeen, bhujia), Agro-products (mustard oil, rice (loose joha and joha) and kanyaka eggs.

Table 11: Detail showing average monthly income of prayassh.

Products	Monthly income (Rs.)	Percentage
Dairy	21000	70
Mustard oil	4000	13.33
Rice	5000	16.66
Total	30000	100%

Figure 16: Showing average monthly income

The above figure 16 shows the average monthly income from major goods of prayash bring from kanyaka. Where a large percentage of monthly income is covered by dairy products about 70%, while mustard oil covered about 13.33% and 16.66% income is covered by rice.

The role of income-generating activities provides a visible solution to the employment creation and poverty alleviation. The income-generating activities are crucial to the economy, as they have provide a major contribute to the officials of kanyaka through prayash in Tezpur over the year. In Tezpur the prayash provides a large no. of income generation activities where they gave employment to the 10 person in prayash centre which means it plays a vital role for the growth of kanyaka agro-farm. Thus, income-generating activities of kanyaka in tezpur play a vital socio-economic role. These activities create a social safety of the people in Tezpur by providing income and employment, particularly to the underemployed or those who cannot find jobs in the formal sector.

7. Impact of Income Generating Activities:

- The income generating activities of kanayaka made a significant impact to the community of surrounding area by creating the job opportunities.
- The income generating activities of kanyaka reduced the unemployment of the people who cannot find the jobs in the formal sector.
- The agriculture sector of kanyaka don't use any kind of pesticides and its provides the pure food or fresh vegetables to the people of local area.
- These income generating activities of kanyaka made a significant development of the surrounding area.
- To produce a large amount of dairy products kanyaka's dairy farm distribute cows to the families of nearby areas which made a significant impact on the livelihood of surrounding villages.
- These income generating activities of kanyaka can made a significant growth of economy of the Sonitpur district.

8. Findings

From the analysis part it had identified that five major income generating activities are found in the study area such as agriculture, dairy farming, poultry farming, swine husbandry and pisciculture. 68 percent of income is from dairy farming, and the contributions of the other activities go like this-agriculture 14 percent, pisciculture 14 percent, poultry farming 3 percent, and swine 1 percent (figure 3) and in the study area the different income generation activities generate a large no of employment where agriculture sector generates employments of 100 person and the contribution of other activities like dairy farming (24 person), poultry farming (4 person), swine husbandry (5 person), and pisciculture generate employment of (5 persons) figure 4.

By going through the tables (table 1 and table 2) and figure (figure 3 and 4) it is found that dairy farming is the main source of income generation and agriculture is the main source of employment creation of kanyaka agro-farm. Where 68% of income is from dairy farming and permanent employment of 100 people is from agriculture sector.

These income generating activities influence the market pattern of surrounding areas, by analysis the market pattern of Tezpur shown in (figure 14) it is found that market pattern of Tezpur is highly influenced by the income generating activities of kanyaka agro-farm, where

the major center of kanyaka is “prayassh” in Tezpur brings major goods like dairy, mustard oil and rice.

Suggestion

The society “Bharalipara Kanyaka Bohumukhi Paam” (Kanyaka) was incorporated September 2016 with an objective of starting multi – cropping projects in 2000 acres of barren land on the flood plains of Jia Bharali River. Its supports various income generating activities which plays an important role to generate income. During the study the researcher has observed a good or wealthy environment of the kanyaka bahumukhi paam, but there are some initiative should be taken for the upliftment of the kanyaka agro-farm such as-

- The paam like kanyaka which is very large in size and supported various income generating activities but in compared to these activities they provide a small unit of employment.
- Kanyaka should focus on the generating of women employment.
- They can earn more income from pisciculture by increasing the artificial ponds.
- The kanyaka is going to be a tourism spot if they take care of its aesthetic view’s.
- The agriculture sector can provide a great extent of income if they focus on it more and use technically developed machines.
- The kanyaka bahumukhi paam is covering a large area which can support more income generating activities.
- The establishment and improvement of poultry rising can lead to a good or wealthy income to the paam.

Concussion:

The present study area work essentially attempted to build up an idea about the income generating activities and their implementation in kanyaka agro-farm. This work involves the general picture of the surveyed area. By analysis it can be said that income generating activities are the vital foundation of the source of livelihood for the communities of surrounding area of kanyaka. It’s the community resource for the people of Jamugurihat and it’s providing all the production of goods to the surrounding markets. The presence of Bharali River also plays an important role to economic activities of kanyaka by providing its water resources. The income generating activities like agriculture, fishery and the animal husbandry directly or indirectly depend on availability of water, especially water from Bharali River. From the above mention analysis, it can be concluded that all the income generating activities

of kanyaka influenced the socio-economic life of the study area in particular to the Jamugurihat, Sonitpur district in general, by providing the employment, producing a large amount of the goods, which influence the market patterns of surrounding area and generate income from these economic activities.

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